

SCALABILITY OF AERODYNAMICS FROM
DEMONSTRATOR TO FULL FLIGHT SCALE OF A
VERTICAL LANDING REUSABLE LAUNCHER

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- SALTO - reusable Strategic Space Launcher Technologies & Operations
- funded by the European Union in the frame of the Horizon Europe programme
- supports the ESA Themis programme
- T1H hop tests
- Technology maturation for T3 and future launcher configurations

26

Project
partners

12

Countries
represented

38

Months to reach
the objective

2

Flight test
demonstrations

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AMORIM
CORK
COMPOSITES

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T1H

Hop Test demonstrator with one Prometheus® Demonstrator to be flown in the frame of SALTO.

High TRL

T3

Reference configuration for future demonstrator version with three Prometheus® engines with more complex trajectory including all flight phases of vertical descent and landing with retro-propulsion

Medium TRL

Future Launcher Configurations

Reference configurations for future launchers with vertical take-off vertical landing. 5 Prometheus® and 9 Prometheus® engines.

Low TRL

T3 vehicle

- 3 Prometheus engines (approx. 120 t thrust)
- Approx. 80 km altitude
- Diameter 3.5 m
- Length approx. 29 m

Configurations inspired by Ariane Group NESTS Study Configurations

- MEDIUM Launcher
 - First Stage:
5 Prometheus (adapted for sea level)
 - Second Stage:
1 Prometheus (adapted for vacuum)
- HEAVY Launcher
 - First Stage:
9 Prometheus (adapted for sea level)
 - Second Stage:
1 Prometheus (adapted for vacuum)

Methodology

- Engine data:
RPA
- Geometry, masses, dimensions and the overall launcher design:
AIOLOS
- Trajectory:
STRATOS
- Aerodynamics:
 - Ascent: **CAC**
(Calculation of Aerodynamic Coefficients)
 - Descent: **AEDB** from the ESA RETPRO project

AIOLOS:

Goldyn, P., Marwege, A., Riehmer, J., Klevanski, J., and Gülhan, A.,
"Preliminary Design of Expendable and Reusable Mixed-Staged Launch Vehicles,"
Journal of Spacecraft and Rockets, Vol. 0, No. 0, 2025, pp. 1-24, 10.2514/1.A36174.

Prometheus Engine (DLR rebuild)

- Start with 100 t thrust and 100 bar pressure in combustion chamber [1]
- Set thrust to 120 t [2]
- Assumption: 120 bar achievable in combustion chamber (Vulcain 2 approx. 117.3 bar [3])

[1] Bonhomme, C. et al. "Prometheus: European next generation liquid rocket engine," *The 68th International Astronautical Congress (IAC)*, Adelaide, Australia, 2017.

[2] Patureau de Mirand, A. et al. "Ariane Next, a vision for a reusable cost efficient European rocket," *8th European Conference for Aeronautics and Space Sciences*, Madrid, Spain, 2019
<https://www.eucass.eu/doi/EUCASS2019-0949.pdf>.

[3] "Website Vulcain 2." <http://cs.astrium.eads.net:80/sp/launcher-propulsion/rocket-engines/vulcain-2-rocket-engine.html> (accessed 05.12.2015).

Engine	Lower Stage Engine	Upper Stage Engine
Characteristics	Adapted for sea level	Adapted for vacuum – 100 as a good compromise
Fuel	LCH4/LOX	LCH4/LOX
Oxidizer Fuel Ratio (OFR)	3.5	3.5
Expansion Area Ratio	20	100
Chamber Pressure	120 bar	120 bar
Exit Pressure	0.756 bar	0.094 bar
Exit Diameter	1.2 m	2.68 m
Isp Vacuum	355.04 s	384.83 s
Isp Sea Level	323.19 s	225.59 s
Thrust Vacuum	1259.287 kN	1312.668 kN
Thrust Sea Level	1146.319 kN	800.142 kN

MEDIUM

- Launch site: Kourou, 5°10'08" N, 52°41'25" W
- Orbit inclination same as launch site's latitude: +5°10'08"
- Design Payload: **16.24 t** to LEO (200 km)
- Payload to GTO: 0.92 t (estimated)
- Gross Lift-off Mass (GLOM): **483.74 t**
- Thrust to Weight Ratio: **1.2**
- Structural fraction dry
 - 6.8 % – stage 1
 - 7.4 % – stage 2

For definitions refer to:
Goldyn, P., Marwege, A., Riehmer, J., Klevanski, J., and Gülhan, A., "Preliminary Design of Expendable and Reusable Mixed-Staged Launch Vehicles,"
Journal of Spacecraft and Rockets, Vol. 0, No. 0, 2025, pp. 1-24, 10.2514/1.A36174.

	Stage1	Stage2
Mass ratio	2.397	5.405
Stage mass share	0.670	0.296
Δv_i	2953	6368
Mass	324094	143409
Mass propellant ascent	281848	130114
Mass propellant descent	14092	0
Mass propellant total	295940	130114
Mass propellant reserve	2959	1301
Mass propellant dead	5919	2602
Mass payload	159649	16239
Mass gross real (GLOM)	483542	159552
Mass structure real wet	42246	13295
Mass structure real dry	22035	10597
Mass structure margin	2203	1060
Structural frac. real wet	0.130	0.093
Structural frac. real dry	0.068	0.074
Height	30.97	26.37
Outer diameter	4.5	4.5
Thrust (vacuum)	6108160	1312670
Thrust (sea level)	5731600	---
Thrust to Weight ratio	1.209	0.839
Reusability index	1.05	1.00

MEDIUM

- Stage separation is at
 - Altitude: 58 km
 - Velocity: 1.625 km/s
 - Mach: 5.1
 - Dyn. Pressure: 512 Pa
- Diameter of 4.5 m
- Length shortened to 30.9 m to fit tanks as computed with AIOLOS

HEAVY

- Launch site: Kourou, 5°10'08" N, 52°41'25" W
- Orbit inclination same as launch site's latitude: +5°10'08"
- Design Payload: **8.1 t to GTO**
- Payload to LEO (200 km): 33 t (estimated)
- Gross Lift-off Weight (GLOW): **877.61 t**
- Thrust to Weight Ratio: **1.2**
- Structural fraction dry
 - 6.0 % – stage 1
 - 5.8 % – stage 2

For definitions refer to:
Goldyn, P., Marwege, A., Riehmer, J., Klevanski, J., and Gülhan, A., "Preliminary Design of Expendable and Reusable Mixed-Staged Launch Vehicles,"
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	Stage1	Stage2
Mass ratio	2.822	8.983
Stage mass share	0.753	0.238
Δv_i	3504	8285
Mass	660659	208803
Mass propellant ascent	566332	192725
Mass propellant descent	42475	0
Mass propellant total	608807	192725
Mass propellant reserve	6088	1927
Mass propellant dead	12176	3855
Mass payload	216866	8150
Mass gross real	877168	216843
Mass structure real wet	94327	16078
Mass structure real dry	39319	12113
Mass structure margin	3932	1211
Structural frac. real wet	0.143	0.077
Structural frac. real dry	0.060	0.058
Height	42.65	29.59
Outer diameter	5.4	5.4
Thrust (vacuum)	10994700	1312670
Thrust (sea level)	10316900	---
Thrust to Weight ratio	1.199	0.617
Reusability index	1.075	1.000

HEAVY

- Stage separation is at
 - Altitude: 77 km
 - Velocity: 2.0 km/s
 - Mach: 7.2
 - Dyn. Pressure: 59 Pa
- Diameter of 5.4 m
- Tanks fitted as computed with AIOLOS

Similarity parameters

- Dynamic pressure: $q_\infty = \frac{1}{2} \rho_\infty u_\infty^2 = \frac{1}{2} p_\infty M_\infty^2 \gamma_\infty$
- Thrust coefficient: $C_T = \frac{F_T}{q_\infty A_{ref}}$
- Momentum Flux Ratio (MFR):

$$MFR = \frac{\rho_e u_e^2}{\rho_\infty u_\infty^2}$$

$$MFR = \frac{F_{t,vac} - A_e p_e}{2 q_\infty A_e}$$

- Connection of MFR and C_T (w/o pressure terms): $C_T = 2 MFR \frac{A_e}{A_{ref}}$
- Connection of MFR and C_T (w/o pressure terms): $C_T = \underbrace{2 MFR \frac{A_e}{A_{ref}}}_{\text{thrust coefficient without pressure terms}} + \underbrace{\frac{p_e}{p_\infty} \frac{A_e}{\frac{1}{2} M_\infty^2 \gamma_\infty A_B}}_{\text{engine exit pressure term}} - \underbrace{\frac{A_e}{\frac{1}{2} M_\infty^2 \gamma_\infty A_B}}_{\text{static pressure term}}$
- Heatflux by Sutton and Graves: $\dot{q} = 1.7414 \cdot 10^{-4} \sqrt{\frac{\rho}{R_n}} \cdot V^3$

T3 MEDIUM HEAVY

Trajectory MEDIUM

- $q_{\max}=120\text{kPa}$, R0L1
- - - $q_{\max}=100\text{kPa}$, R1L1
- ⋯ $q_{\max}=100\text{kPa}$, R2L1
- ⋯ $q_{\max}=100\text{kPa}$, R3L1

- $q_{\max}=120\text{kPa}$, R0L1
- - - $q_{\max}=100\text{kPa}$, R1L1
- ⋯ $q_{\max}=100\text{kPa}$, R2L1
- ⋯ $q_{\max}=100\text{kPa}$, R3L1
- · - · T3

Fuel Consumption:
 120 kPa – R0L1: 4.3 t
 100 kPa – R1L1: 5.7 t
 100 kPa – R2L1: 7.2 t
 100 kPa – R3L1: 8.7 t

Trajectory MEDIUM

Trajectory MEDIUM

- qmax=120kPa, R0L1
- - - qmax=100kPa, R1L1
- ... qmax=100kPa, R2L1
- · - qmax=100kPa, R3L1
- - - T3

- qmax=120kPa, R0L1
- - - qmax=100kPa, R1L1
- ... qmax=100kPa, R2L1
- · - qmax=100kPa, R3L1
- - - T3

$$MFR = \frac{F_{t,vac} - A_e p_e}{2 q_\infty A_e}$$

$$q_\infty = \frac{1}{2} \rho_\infty u_\infty^2 = \frac{1}{2} p_\infty M_\infty^2 \gamma_\infty$$

Trajectory MEDIUM

- $q_{\max}=120\text{kPa}$, R0L1
- - - $q_{\max}=100\text{kPa}$, R1L1
- ⋯ $q_{\max}=100\text{kPa}$, R2L1
- ⋯ $q_{\max}=100\text{kPa}$, R3L1
- · - T3

- $q_{\max}=120\text{kPa}$, R0L1
- - - $q_{\max}=100\text{kPa}$, R1L1
- ⋯ $q_{\max}=100\text{kPa}$, R2L1
- ⋯ $q_{\max}=100\text{kPa}$, R3L1
- · - T3

Heat Loads:
 120 kPa – R0L1: 388 kW/m²
 100 kPa – R1L1: 309 kW/m²
 100 kPa – R2L1: 374 kW/m²
 100 kPa – R3L1: 374 kW/m²

Trajectory HEAVY

Fuel Consumption:
 100 kPa – R2L3: 29.7 t
 100 kPa – R3L3: 28.8 t
 120 kPa – R2L3: 26.6 t
 120 kPa – R3L3: 26.2 t

Trajectory HEAVY

- q_max=120kPa, R3L3
- - - q_max=100kPa, R3L3
- ⋯ q_max=120kPa, R2L3
- ⋯ q_max=100kPa, R2L3
- · - T3

- q_max=120kPa, R3L3
- - - q_max=100kPa, R3L3
- ⋯ q_max=120kPa, R2L3
- ⋯ q_max=100kPa, R2L3
- · - T3

Trajectory HEAVY

- $q_{max}=120\text{kPa}$, R3L3
- - - $q_{max}=100\text{kPa}$, R3L3
- ... $q_{max}=120\text{kPa}$, R2L3
- · - $q_{max}=100\text{kPa}$, R2L3
- - - T3

- $q_{max}=120\text{kPa}$, R3L3
- - - $q_{max}=100\text{kPa}$, R3L3
- ... $q_{max}=120\text{kPa}$, R2L3
- · - $q_{max}=100\text{kPa}$, R2L3
- - - T3

Trajectory HEAVY

Heat Loads:
 120 kPa – R3L3: 351 kW/m²
 100 kPa – R3L3: 327 kW/m²
 120 kPa – R2L3: 275 kW/m²
 100 kPa – R2L3: 205 kW/m²

Summary and outlook

Summary

- MEDIUM and HEAVY configurations based on Ariane NESTS Study
- MEDIUM with 5 Prometheus engines, HEAVY with 9 Prometheus engines
- Re-entry burn: T3 provides especially good similarity for MEDIUM
- For MEDIUM Re-entry burn could be skipped
- Landing burn: excellent similarity (Momentum Flux Ratio and Thrust Coefficient)

Outlook

- Computation of (low-fidelity) Aerodynamic Databases (AEDBs) for both configurations
- Flight dynamics and mission analysis by DEIMOS
- Analysis on structural integration of landing legs and grid fins by MT Aerospace

Tim Horchler

Unsteady Pressure Loads on T3

Monday 11:40 am – 12:00 pm: session 1.3

Mariasole Laureti

Aerothermal Loads on T3

Monday 3:20 pm – 3:40 pm: session 1.5

Jan Vos

Aerodynamic Database of T3

Monday 3:20 pm – 3:40 pm: session 1.7

Ansgar Marwege

Aerodynamic Models of T3

Monday 4:40 pm – 6:00 pm: session 1.11

Gabriele De Zaiacomo

Flight Dynamics of T3

Tuesday 3:40 pm – 4:00 pm: session 2.13

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Thank you!

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